

VOL. 44

JAN 2023

SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SURVEY OF ARACHNIDA

SANSA Newsletter 44

SANSA NEWSLETTER

SANSA –ACTIVITIES 2022

During SANSA surveys, large numbers of specimens are sampled, resulting in a rich database of South African species. During 2022 we focused on the following activities:

- to **revise** and describe new genera;
- to get **new species** described;
- to provide new morphological information based on **live specimens**;
- to get South African fauna listed on the **World Spider Catalog** (WSC);
- to publish new data on species **behaviour**;
- to publish results of SANSA **surveys**;
- to produce identification guides and keys;
- to make all the information available on **Zenodo** – a general-purpose open repository; and
- to publish a quarterly newsletter.

This has resulted in the following activities in 2022:

GENERA

- ◆ New genus: *Afrodrassex*.
- ◆ New names: *Deinopus* now *Asianopis* (Deinopidae); *Ocyale* now *Hippasosa* (Lycosidae)
- ◆ Revised genera: *Andromma*, *Orthobula*, *Leptodrassex*, *Leptopilos*, *Voraptus* (now Pisauridae).
- ◆ Nine genera were newly recorded from South Africa: Araneidae (*Acantharachne*, *Bijoaraneus*); Ctenidae (*Bowie*); Philodromidae (*Gephyrota*); Prodidomidae (*Namundra*); Salticidae (*Vicirionessa*); Theridiidae (*Episinus*) and Thomisidae (*Hewittia*, *Parasmodix*).

SPECIES

- ◆ 11 new species: Gnaphosidae (7); Prodidomidae (1); Trachelidae (2); Trochanteriidae (1).
- ◆ Number of species listed from South Africa on WSC for first time = **26**.
- ◆ New taxonomic papers from South Africa listed on WSC for 2022 = **35**.

BEHAVIOUR

- ◆ New behavioural data on 22 species published.

PUBLISHED SURVEYS

- ◆ Surveys published: Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, Tierberg (Long Term Ecological Research site), Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve and Ndumo Game Reserve.

IN THIS ISSUE

SANSA activity 2022	1
Leptodrassinae new spp.	2
<i>Ikuma</i> sp.	3
Synotaxidae	3
<i>Thyene mutica</i>	4
<i>Brancus</i> sp. now <i>Vicirionessa</i>	4
<i>Deinopis</i> now <i>Asianopis</i>	5
Field observations	5
<i>Andromma raffrayi</i>	6
Mariepskop	7
Okavango Delta	8
Recent publications	9
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i>	10-13
<i>Romphaea affinis</i>	14-16
<i>Trichopagis manicata</i>	17-19
<i>Hippasosa guttata</i>	20-22
Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve	23-31

EDITOR

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman
dippenaaransie@gmail.com

EDITORIAL COMMITTEE

Rudi Steenkamp
rudolphsteinkampf@gmail.com

Ruan Booysen
booysenr@ufs.ac.za

Stefan Foord
stefan@foord.co

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/>

NEW PUBLICATION

First records of the small ground spider genera of Gnaphosidae (Leptodrassinae) in South Africa

HADDAD C.R. & BOOYSEN R. 2022. The ground spider genera *Leptodrassex* Murphy, 2007 and *Leptopilos* Levy, 2009 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) in Southern Africa, including the description of a new genus and seven new species. *Zootaxa* 5941(1): 1–32.

The Leptodrassinae is a small subfamily of ground spiders (Gnaphosidae), currently known from only four genera. Previously, only four species of Leptodrassinae have been described from the Afrotropical Region, all belonging to *Leptodrassus*.

They are peculiar tiny gnaphosids found in various biomes and microhabitats. They are particularly interesting because of the consistently small size of the adults (generally 2–3 mm) and their pale colouration without markings, except for black pigment in the ocular region. They were predominantly sampled from the ground by pitfalls, litter sifting, beneath rocks or from grass tussocks, and only rarely from woody vegetation by beating and fogging. Specimens of *Afrodrassex balrog* were collected inside houses and gardens in the Free State, where they were active at night.

Haddad and Booysen (2022) recorded three genera of Leptodrassinae from Southern Africa for the first time. They described *Afrodrassex* Haddad & Booysen, 2022, a new genus with two new species, *Leptodrassex* Murphy, 2007 (two new species) and *Leptopilos* Levy, 2009 (three new species).

GENUS AFRODRASSEX

- *Afrodrassex balrog* from Free State, South Africa, and Angola (both sexes).
- *Afrodrassex catharinae* from northern KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (both sexes).

GENUS LEPTODRASSEX

- *Leptodrassex murphyi* from KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, and Mozambique (both sexes).
- *Leptodrassex capensis* from Western Cape, South Africa (only female).

GENUS LEPTOPILOS

- *Leptopilos butleri* widely distributed in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Botswana (both sexes).
- *Leptopilos digitus* widespread in the western half of South Africa (both sexes).
- *Leptopilos vasivulva* only known from a small area in northern Limpopo, South Africa, and south-western Zimbabwe, and south-eastern Botswana (both sexes).

Leptodrassex murphyi female and male from Bloemfontein. Photos: Ruan Booysen

Afrodrassex balrog

Leptopilos butleri

Leptodrassex sp. male from Roodeplaat Photo: P. Webb

Distribution of *Afrodrassex balrog* (black stars), *A. catharinae* (inverted triangle), *Leptodrassex capensis* (black triangles), and *L. murphyi* (open circles) in Southern and Central Africa (after Haddad & Booysen, 2022).

NEW PUBLICATION

ZONSTEIN S. & MARUSIK Y.M. 2022. Redescription of the poorly known genus *Ikuma* Lawrence, with synonymy and description of a new species from Namibia (Araneae, Palpimanidae). *African Invertebrates* 3(2): 105–119.

ABSTRACT

The spider genus *Ikuma* Lawrence, 1938, endemic to Namibia, is rediagnosed and redescribed based on the characteristics of both species originally included in the genus and of the newly described *I. larseni* sp. nov. A new synonymy is proposed: *I. squamata* Lawrence, 1938, described from a sole female, is recognised a junior synonym of the type species *I. spiculosa* (Lawrence, 1927), based on a single juvenile. The currently described *I. larseni* sp. nov. differs from the generotype in the eye arrangement, structure of the abdominal scuta, and details of the colouration. The copulatory organs of both males and females belonging to *Ikuma* are studied, described, and depicted for the first time. The previously known genus range confined to the far north of Namibia extends to the mid-western part of South Africa.

Eye pattern. After Zonstein & Marusik (2022).

NEW SPECIES FROM SOUTH AFRICA

As part of the biodiversity survey in the arid western interior of South Africa by Charles Haddad and his team, a strange palpimanid was collected that was identified as a *Ikuma* species that was collected in the Richtersveld National Park.

Ikuma sp. from Richtersveld National Park. Photos: Ruan Booysen.

MYSTERY GREEN SPIDER (THERIDIIDAE) RATHER SYNOTAXIDAE

In SANSA Newsletter 39: 3–4 we reported on this strange green spiders as photographed by Anne Metcalf (metcalfp@tiscali.co.za) in KwaZulu-Natal. She also photographed the egg sac with about 20 eggs that was covered with a thin silk layer and deposited in a sac shaped like a bird nest on a leaf.

In an article by Agnarsson (2003), a similar photo of a female spider resembling our mystery spider with a bird nest egg sac was listed in the genus *Synotaxus* Simon, 1895 in the family Synotaxidae.

In 1990, *Synotaxus* was transferred to the family Synotaxidae and the Cyatholipidae are recognised as its sister group (Agnarsson, 2003). They are recognised by the long abdomen that extends beyond the spinnerets, and the long, fragile legs. A field note states the colour to be light green. Body and legs covered with long, fine, semi-erect setae that are easily lost. Carapace wide and flat, both eye rows recurved. Sternum as wide or wider than long and usually very convex, widely separating hind coxae.

Their web, guarding egg sac, and general somatic morphology (absence of tarsal comb on leg IV) make *Synotaxus* unlike any theridiid.

AGNARSSON I. 2003. The phylogenetic placement and circumscription of the genus *Synotaxus* (Araneae: Synotaxidae), a new species from Guyana, and notes on theridioid phylogeny. *Invertebrate Systematics* 17(6): 719–734.

Note: Agnarsson (pers com) confirmed that this is possibly a new genus in the Synotaxidae. The species is known from the Eastern and Western Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, and Mpumalanga.

However, it is very important that specimens are sampled for taxonomic research.

Figs 1–2. Female photographed from KwaZulu-Natal, with bird-nest egg sac. Photos: Anne Metcalf.

SALTICIDAE: NEW COMBINATION AND GENUS

WESOŁOWSKA W. & RUSSELL-SMITH A. 2022. Jumping spiders from Ivory Coast collected by J.-C. Ledoux (Araneae, Salticidae). *European Journal of Taxonomy* 841: 1–143. doi:10.5852/ejt.2022.841.1943

In a recent paper by Wesolowska & Russell-Smith (2022) on the jumping spiders of the Ivory Coast, several new species and genera were described but only two species are known from South Africa.

1. NEW COMBINATION

Brancus muticus Simon, 1902 = *Thyene mutica* (Simon, 1902)

The species is distinguishable by the characteristic pattern composed of five large patches on the eye field, especially clear in females (Figs 1–2). Recorded from Guinea, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Congo, and South Africa.

Figs 1–2. *Thyene mutica*. 1. Female. 2. Immature male. Photos: Vida van der Walt.

2. NEW GENUS

Vicirionessa Wesolowska & Russell-Smith 2022

Brancus mustelus Simon, 1902 = *Vicirionessa mustela* (Simon, 1902)

Diagnosis and affinities: Medium-sized spiders, measuring 5–10 mm (Figs 1–4). Carapace pear-shaped, widest at half of the length of the thoracic area. Abdomen elongated, narrowing towards the end. Chelicerae unidentate. Legs long, first and second pair longer and stouter than others, often covered with long, thick hairs, spines numerous. Palpal organ with elongated bulb, medium-length embolus originates on its prolateral side and quite large tibial apophysis. Females have epigynes with two large depressions, the edges of which are strongly sclerotised.

Vicirionessa is closely related to both *Evarcha* Simon, 1902 and *Hyllus* C.L. Koch, 1846. Unfortunately, both of these latter genera are poorly defined and each contains a significant diversity in genital morphology. *Vicirionessa* is known from 12 species, all distributed in Africa, with only one, *Vicirionessa mustela* (Simon, 1902), so far recorded from South Africa.

Figs 1–4. *Vicirionessa mustela*. 1–2. Female. 3–4. Male. Photos: Vida vd Walt.

A drawing in the *Spider Families of the World* (Jocqué & Dippenaar Schoeman, 2007) shows a female of Synotaxidae carrying her egg sac in her chelicerae. It is a small, delicate spider with slender legs that closely correspond with the images taken of a spider with an egg sac by Andrea Sander in KwaZulu-Natal.

NOTE: In the first Theridiidae Identification Guide, the species was listed as a possible *Exalbidion* species but we need sampled material to determine the correct placement.

COULD THIS BE ANOTHER SYNOTAXID?

Figures 1–3. 1–2. Female with egg sac (Photo: Andrea Sander). 3. Female (Photo: Desire Pelsler).

DEINOPIDAE: SA *DEINOPIS* NOW *ASIANOPIS*

LIN Y., SHAO L., HÄNGGI A., CALEB J.T.D., KOH J.K.H., JÄGER P., LI S. 2020. *Asianopsis* gen. nov., a new genus of the spider family Deinopidae from Asia. *ZooKeys* 911: 67–99.

CHAMBERLAND L., AGNARSSON I., QUAYLE I.L., RUDDY T., STARRETT J. & BOND J.E. 2022. Biogeography and eye size evolution of the ogre-faced spiders. *Scientific Reports* 12(17769): 1–15.

Deinopidae is a small family with three genera and 67 extant species from the tropical regions of the world. Four species have so far been reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2020). In 2020, a new genus, *Asianopsis* Lin & Li, 2020, was proposed for Asian species and in a recent publication by Chamberland *et al.* (2022), all the *Deinopsis* species reported from South Africa were transferred to *Asianopsis*.

- *Asianopsis anchietae* (Brito Capello, 1867)
- *A. aspectans* (Pocock, 1900)
- *A. cornigera* (Gerstaecker, 1873)
- *A. cylindrica* (Pocock, 1898)

Asianopsis differs from *Deinopsis* as follows:

- presence of a prominent setal fringe;
- embolic tip with an apophysis or folded apically;
- median apophysis distal lobe small and with a basal lobe;
- female chelicerae with many denticles between the pro-marginal and retromarginal teeth or without denticles;
- epigynal median plate lateral margins anchor shaped; and
- spermathecal duct narrow throughout its length.

Asianopsis anchietae. Photo: A. Louw.

A. cornigera. Photo: Vida vd Walt.

Asianopsis aspectans. Photo: Peter Webb.

Some interesting field observations from Jakkalswater in the Northern Cape

Fig. 1. A female *Theuma fusca* (Prodidomidae) was photographed at Jakkalswater in the Northern Cape by the late Peter Webb. She was found in a nest of honey ants (Figs 2–3), where she was running around between the ants, apparently without causing alarm. Photos: Peter Webb.

Fig. 1. *Mexcala* sp. (Salticidae) females were photographed in an area (Fig. 3) at Jakkalswater in the Northern Cape associated with *Camponotus* ants (Fig. 2). In Fig. 3 the spiders were found under the stone marked with blue, while the ants were found under the stone marked with red. A female was found between the honey ants, apparently without causing alarm. Research showed that *Mexcala* spp. feed on the ants. Photos: Peter Webb.

Revision of *Andromma* Simon, 1893 (Araneae: Liocranidae)

BOSSELAERS J. & JOCQUÉ R. 2022. Studies in the Liocranidae (Araneae): revision of *Andromma* Simon, 1893. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 850: 1–78. <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2022.850.1997>

Andromma raffrayi Photo: Charles Haddad

Until now, *Andromma* was considered a small and poorly defined genus. Simon described two additional species: *Andromma raffrayi* Simon, 1899 from South Africa and *Andromma anochetorum* Simon, 1909 from Gabon. In his descriptions of the latter two species, Simon (1899, 1909) mentioned the myrmecophilous habits of *Andromma* for the first time. Lessert (1936) described *Andromma raffrayi* subsp. *inhacorensis* from Mozambique, based on small, unconvincing differences from the parent species. Fage (1936) added the termitophilous *Andromma bouvieri* from Kenya. In this paper, 19 additional species of *Andromma* are described all collected from the African continent.

SOUTH AFRICAN SPECIES

Only one species *Andromma raffrayi* and a subspecies *Andromma raffrayi* subsp. *inhacorensis* was recognized by Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2021) from South Africa. In this paper by Bosselaers & Jocque (2022) *A. raffrayi* Simon, 1899 are redescribed and the subspecies *A. raffrayi inhacorensis* Lessert, 1936 is considered a synonym of the nominal species.

The species is myrmecophilous free running ground dwellers. In Cape of Good Hope some type material was collected deep within ant nests of *Plagiolepis* (= *Anoplolepis*) *fallax* (Mayr, 1865), together with a specimen of *Pentaplatarthrus pausoides* Westwood, 1833 (Carabidae). Tucker (1923) collected males and females of *A. raffrayi* from nests of *Plagiolepis custodiens* ants in the Western Cape Province, South Africa.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2021. The Liocranidae of South Africa. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6735570>.

FAGE L. 1936. Une araignée termitophile, *Andromma bouvieri*, n. sp. In: *Livre jubilaire de M. Eugène-Louis Bouvier*: 83–87. Fermin-Didot et Cie, Paris.

LESSERT R. DE 1936. Araignées de l'Afrique orientale portugaise, recueillies par MM. P. Lesne et B.-B. Cott. *Revue suisse de Zoologie* 43: 207–306

SIMON E. 1899. Description d'une araignée myrmécophile du Cap de Bonne-Espérance (*Andromma Raffrayi* n. sp.). *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France* 4: 179-181.

TUCKER R.W.E. 1923 The Drassidae of South Africa. *Annals of the South African Museum* 19:251–438.

Figures 1-5. *Andromma raffrayi*. 1. Eye pattern. 2. Epigyne. 3. Palp. 4. Male habitus. 5. known distribution. Photos: Charles Haddad

COMPLETED STUDENT PROJECT

Invertebrate species of the Mariepskop Summit, Mpumalanga

Mariepskop is a semi-inselberg located on the border of both the Mpumalanga and Limpopo provinces, situated on the north-eastern side of the Drakensberg and forming part of the Afromontane Region. It forms part of a 5 000-km-long, semi-continuous Southern African mountain range system, known as the Great Escarpment (Fig. 1).

A fynbos-type shrubland similar to that of the Cape Floristic Region (CFR) also occurs on Mariepskop. These typical fynbos taxa and growth forms are not restricted to the Cape and can also be found in montane grasslands and high-altitude fynbos in the Afromontane Region. The eastern Drakensberg Escarpment is therefore a floristic link between the CFR and the remainder of the Afromontane Region.

Very little is known about the invertebrate fauna of Mariepskop; and a critical assessment was required to determine which unique and/or endemic species occur here. Two Arthropoda groups – Heteroptera and Araneae (Arachnida) – were surveyed, focusing on the summit (above 1 800 m) of Mariepskop, in order to assess the invertebrates.

The objectives of the study were to:

- establish a list of genera and species on the summit of Mariepskop above 1800 m.a.s.l.;
- explore the species composition of the recorded invertebrates sampled in different vegetation communities with those of other close-by vegetation types; and
- investigate the geographical distribution of the invertebrates to determine if any affinities exist with the fauna of the Natal Drakensberg Afromontane fynbos and the fynbos of the Cape.

During three surveys between 2013 and 2014, six different collecting methods were used to capture a wider range of species from all the field layers, including a specially designed ramp pitfall trap (Fig. 6). Seventeen study sites spread across the four plant communities were sampled (Figs 2–4).

Forty-three spider families, represented by 102 genera and 128 species, have been collected. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (22 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (12 spp.) and Araneidae (9 spp.), while 18 families are represented by singletons. Thirty-eight species from 21 families were collected that probably have an association with fynbos vegetation; they are, however, not necessarily restricted to fynbos vegetation.

On Mariepskop, approximately 5.8% of the total South African spider fauna are protected. Two species (1.6%), *Hortipes licnophorus* and *Cheiramiona debeeri*, are presently endemic to Mariepskop and the Mpumalanga province, while 2.3% near Mpumalanga endemics are protected on the summit. The high number (10.2%) of indeterminate species may be indicative of unique fauna presently protected on Mariepskop.

Fig. 1. Mariepskop area sampled

Fig. 2. Grassland community

Fig 3. Shrubland community

Fig 3. Forest community

Fig 5. Rocky community

Figs 2–6. 2–5. The four plant communities sampled. 6. Custom-designed ramp pitfall trap. Photos: L. Taylor.

TAYLOR L. 2020. Invertebrate species of the Mariepskop Summit, Mpumalanga province, South Africa: Affinities with Afromontane Natal Drakensberg fynbos and Cape fynbos. Dissertation (MSc Environmental Ecology), University of Pretoria (unpublished).

STUDENT PROJECT

Exploring terrestrial invertebrate diversity in the Okavango Delta, Botswana

The Okavango River basin is one of the largest undeveloped, unexplored river basins in the world. The water feedings this iconic natural system starts its journey in the Angolan midlands, and traverses vast distances, crossing three countries, terminating in central Botswana in the Makgadikgadi pans. Designated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site, the Okavango-delta, with its fauna and flora that reside within its complex meandering channels and islands, is a globally renowned tourist destination for those looking to explore the 600 000 hectares of pristine wilderness protected and managed, in part, by local community trusts. Although researchers have done well to document the large mammals, birds, amphibians, and fish within the delta, some of the smaller terrestrial inhabitants have remained under the radar.

During his fieldwork, MSc candidate Michiel Grobler at UCT aimed to continue the work done by invertebrate researchers exploring and documenting the terrestrial invertebrate diversity of the delta. Working from the Mopiri Research Camp, run by the Botswana Wild Bird Trust, Michiel explored the impacts of anthropogenic disturbances (fire and livestock grazing) on invertebrate communities, focusing on four main groups: Hymenoptera (ants and parasitoid wasps), Collembola (springtails), and Araneae (spiders). Using a combination of systematic sampling, he deployed 120 pitfall traps and collected 120 litter samples for Tullgren extraction in November 2021 and February 2022 (Figs 1–2). Additionally, more than 200 specimens of wasps and spiders were collected opportunistically.

After months of sorting, 18 families represented by 71 species of Araneae were identified through the assistance of arachnologist Prof. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. This joint effort saw 17 new records for the region, adding to the >228 species of Araneae known from Botswana. Some interesting observation included species such as *Trichonephila senegalensis* (Fig. 3), *Thyene ogdeni* (Fig. 4), and *Thomisus granulatus* (Fig. 5).

Further analysis will explore the community dynamics of recently burnt and continuously grazed sites, to establish a baseline for future researchers. It is critical for the research community to gain as much information as possible on the invertebrate communities that underpin many of the ecological processes that ensure the continued working of this unique wetland system. The survival and protection of this system will only be ensured if we continue to improve our knowledge and understanding of the critters that crawl in the undergrowth.

Contact: Michiel Grobler at michieljgrob@gmail.com

Figs 1–5. 1. Michiel Grobler in the field near Mopiri Rest Camp, Botswana, checking the pitfall traps. 2. Tullgren funnel extraction. 3. Araneidae *Trichonephila senegalensis*. 4. Salticidae *Thyene ogdeni*. 5. Thomisidae *Thomisus granulatus* male. Photos: Michiel Grobler

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

- BIRD T., WARMENHOVE C., AUCAMP M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2022. Cheliceral flashing not only in wolf spiders (Araneae: Lycosidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 31–32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146546>
- BOSELAERS J. & JOCQUÉ R. 2022. Studies in the Liocranidae (Araneae): revision of *Andromma* Simon, 1893. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 850: 1–78.
- CHAMBERLAND L., AGNARSSON I., QUAYLE I.L., RUDDY T., STARRETT J. & BOND J.E. 2022. Biogeography and eye size evolution of the ogre-faced spiders. *Scientific Report* 12(17769): 1–15. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-22157-5
- DIAZ C. JR. & ROFF J. 2022. Mechanics of the prey capture technique of the South African grassland bolas spider, *Cladomelea akermani*. *Insects* 13(12): <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects13121118>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., DEAN W.R.J. & MILTON S.J. 2022. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Tierberg Long Term Ecological Research site, Prince Albert, Western Cape, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 21–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146693>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., & HADDAD C.R. 2022. The first record of *Apochinomma elongatum* Haddad, 2013 from South Africa (Arachnida: Corinnidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 7–8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146341>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., WIESE L., & WEBB P. 2022. First record of *Leucauge argyrescens* Benoit, 1978 from South Africa (Araneae: Tetragnathidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 11–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146657>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LOTZ L.N., ROUX C. & WEBB P. 2022. First records of the white widow spider *Latrodectus pallidus* O.P.-Cambridge, 1872 from South Africa (Araneae: Theridiidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 29–30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146600>
- Dippenaar-Schoeman A.S., Sander A. & Webb P. 2022. First record of *Acantharachne seydeli* Giltay, 1935 from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 9–10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146479>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2022. Observations on the trapdoor spider *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Purcell, 1902) (Araneae: Cyrtauchenidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 18–20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146286>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2022. First record of the crab spider *Synema simoneae* Lessert, 1919 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 13–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146423>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2022. More on the crab spider *Phrynarachne melloleitaoi* Lessert, 1933 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 43: 15–17. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7146383>
- HADDAD C.R. 2022. A redescription of *Voraptus affinis* Lessert, 1925 (Araneae: Pisauridae), with comments on the placement of the genus. *Arthropoda Selecta* 31(4): 496–500.
- HADDAD C.R. & BOOYSEN R. 2022. The ground spider genera *Leptodrassex* Murphy, 2007 and *Leptopilos* Levy, 2009 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) in Southern Africa, including the description of a new genus and seven new species. *Zootaxa* 5941(1): 1–32. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5194.1.1
- PEKÁR S., MARTIŠOVÁ M., TÓTHOVÁ S.A. & HADDAD C.R. 2022. Mimetic accuracy and co-evolution of mimetic traits in ant-mimicking species. *iScience* 25, 105126, October 21, 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105126>
- VENTER C., HADDAD C.R. 2022 & CODRON D. 2022. A novel approach to determine the surface area of buckspoor spider webs and other irregular-shaped two-dimensional objects. *MethodsX* 9 (2022) 101904. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2022.101904>
- WESOŁOWSKA W. & RUSSELL-SMITH A. 2022. Jumping spiders from Ivory Coast collected by J.-C. Ledoux (Araneae, Salticidae). *European Journal of Taxonomy* 841: 1–143. doi:10.5852/ejt.2022.841.1943
- ZONSTEIN S. & MARUSIK Y. M. 2022. Redescription of the poorly known genus *Ikuma* Lawrence, with synonymy and description of a new species from Namibia (Araneae, Palpimanidae). *African Invertebrates* 63(2): 105–119.

22ND INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF ARACHNOLOGY

- Intendencia de Montevideo
- Avenida 18 de Julio 1360, PC 11200, Montevideo, Uruguay
- 5th to 11th March 2023
- Email: 22ica.uy@gmail.com
- Facebook: 22nd International Congress of Arachnology
- Instagram: [@22ica23](https://www.instagram.com/22ica23)
- Twitter: [@22ica23](https://twitter.com/22ica23)

New information on the green tree crab spider *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, J. van Zyl², A. Sander³, B. Blake³, & P. Webb^{2†}

¹University of Venda, ²SANSA team members Gauteng, ³SANSA team members KwaZulu-Natal

ABSTRACT: The genus *Oxytate* L. Koch, 1878 is represented by 30 species and six are known from the Afrotropical Region. One of the species, *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886), is found throughout the region. New Information on their morphology, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa is here provided.

Key words: agroecosystems, biodiversity, egg sac, avocado orchard, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oxytate* L. Koch, 1878 is known from 30 species, of which six have been recorded from the Afrotropical Region. Information on these species described between 1886 and 1964 is limited and outdated (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and one of them was identified as *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886).

This African endemic species was described by Simon (1886) as *Dieta argenteooculata* from Zanzibar, but Song *et al.* (1982) considered *Oxytate* a senior synonym of *Dieta* Simon, 1880 and the species was transferred to *Oxytate*. It has since then been sampled from several countries in the Afrotropical Region. Little is still known about them in South Africa and the aim of this paper is to provide information on their morphology based on live specimens, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Voucher specimens of *O. argenteooculata* sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. Numerous photographs were submitted by the public for identification as part of the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Oxytate argenteooculata (Simon, 1886)

Dieta argenteooculata Simon, 1886: 179 (f); Simon, 1895: 981(f); Lessert, 1919: 99 (m); Lessert, 1928: 306 (f); Lessert, 1943: 311 (m).

Dieta argenteooculata Jézéquel, 1964: 1107 (f).

Oxytate argenteooculata Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014: 243; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: part 2: 1819 (m & f).

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female and male 5–8 mm. Live members are recognised by their green bodies decorated with red spots, but the green colour fades in alcohol. The green of the body varies from translucent pale green (Figs 1–2) to darker green (Fig. 3), while the colour of the legs in males varies from green to pale brown (Figs 12–13). Carapace: circular, flattened, with thin reddish brown marginal band; the colour of the marginal band varies from reddish brown (Fig. 14) to brown (Fig. 23); band sometimes absent in juveniles; four small reddish spots are present on both sides of fovea (Figs 1–3), sometimes only two (Fig. 23); chelicerae wide; eyes in two

Figs 1–3. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 1. Female anterior view of eyes. 2. Female on leaf, dorsal view. 3. Female dorsal view. Photos: 1–2. Bruce Blake. 3. Peter Webb.

Figs 4–11. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 4. Line drawing, male palp. 5. Male palp, retrotibial apophysis. 6–7. Male palp dorsal view and lateral view. 8. Epigyne. 9. Line drawing, epigyne. 10. Line drawing, eye pattern. 11. Line drawing, carapace lateral view. Photos: 4. Lessert (1919). 5. Lessert (1943). 6–8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 9. Jézéquel (1964). 10–11. Simon (1895).

recurved rows (Figs 1 & 10), anterior row shorter than posterior row; eyes on small, flat, white tubercles; median eyes smaller than lateral eyes; anterior lateral eyes the largest (Figs 1 & 23); median ocular area longer than wide.

Abdomen green, elongated with spotted appearance; posterior third with transverse paired rows of 6–8 thick setae (Fig. 3). Legs spotted; distal segments paler; two anterior legs longer than the posterior legs; tibiae and metatarsi with biseriate long macrosetae (Fig. 18); tarsal claws long and narrow with 8 to 13 teeth; femora of all the legs with erect strong setae anterior laterally (Figs 1–2). Male palp with long retrolateral apophysis with tip curved (Figs 4–7); atrium of epigyne heart shaped (Figs 8–9).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Zanzibar; Tanzania (Kibonoto Kilimandjaro) (Lessert, 1919); Democratic Republic of the Congo (Faradje, Medje, Poko) (Lessert, 1928); Zambia (iNaturalist); Eswatini; South Africa (NCA); Mozambique.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Thyspunt, (-34.206, 24.708); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.2). **Gauteng:** Cullinan Premier Game Farm (-25.67, 28.48); Irene (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park; uMkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.61, 30.38). **Limpopo:** Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.1); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.01); Gundani Forest (-22.655, 30.532). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Glenwood (-25.48, 30.92); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Schagen (-25.43, 30.8).

North West: Hartebeespoort (-25.6, 27.82). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Uitzicht Annex (-34.0, 23.33); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38). Knysna, Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.33).

LIFE STYLE

They are free-living plant dwellers and were sampled during SANSa surveys from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), and Thicket biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and beating methods.

During surveys in agroecosystems in the Mpumalanga province in South Africa, knock-sprays were used to sample spiders in avocado and macadamia orchards. In the avocado orchards, *O. argenteooculata* was the most abundant species sampled, representing 22.2% of all spiders collected during the year-long survey (n=826) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005). The species were commonly observed on leaves of the avocado trees, where they blend in with their green flattened bodies. *Oxytate* specimens are not commonly found and this was the first time that an *Oxytate* species has been collected in such high numbers from orchards in Africa. The adults were sampled throughout the year, and juveniles were sampled from May until October.

The surveys in macadamia orchards were undertaken during the same period in the same area but yielded only 12 specimens from three orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001). Further surveys in agroecosystems showed that the species has also been sampled from citrus orchards and from tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) as well as from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999) but in lower numbers. They have been observed to feed on a variety of insects (Fig. 22) and mites.

The second author photographed a female with her egg sac in Heidelberg, Gauteng. The white, round sac was deposited on the ventral side of a leaf. The egg sac was then covered with several thin layers of silk covering a large area of the leaf (Figs 15–16). The female took up position on the egg sac (Fig. 16), where she stayed to guard it until the eggs hatched (Fig. 17). In the same area a juvenile spider was photographed preparing to balloon (Figs 18–20).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

The species has a wide distribution in the Afrotropical Region and in South Africa it was sampled from eight of the nine provinces. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

There are no known threats to the species and in South Africa it is recorded from several protected areas. The following survey results were published: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.*, 2008); Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 201) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009).

Figs 12–23. *Oxytate argenteooculata*: 12. Male from Kloof. 13. Immature male from Kloof. 14. Female from Irene. 15–17. Female with egg sac and spiderlings from Heidelberg. 18–19. Spider from Heidelberg in process to start ballooning. 21. Spider as found on leaves. 22. Female busy feeding. 23. Female eye pattern. Photos: 12. Bruce Blake. 13 & 23. Andrea Sander. 14. Peter Webb. 15–22. Johan van Zyl.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR S.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MODIBA M.A. & KHOZA T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10–17.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publishers, 424 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., HADDAD C.R., & LE ROUX E. 2021. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape province, South Africa. *SANSА Newsletter* 38: 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5947479>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2022. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Thomisidae of South Africa (part 2). Version 2: 1–67.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSА): review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13(1/2): 121–127.

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A. & PRENDINI L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 1–9.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: a review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & FOORD S.H. 2005. Spiders in avocado orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 11: 8–16.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2001. Spiders in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 7: 36–46.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE L. 2022. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Thyspunt, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 23–29.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2020. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Addo Elephant National Park in the Eastern Cape province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1), a1578. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v62i1.1578>.
- FOORD S.H., MAFADZA M.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN RENSBURG B.J. 2008. Small scale heterogeneity in spider (Arachnida: Araneae) species composition and assemblage structure in the Soutpansberg, South Africa. *African Zoology* 43: 156–174.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., SCHOEMAN C., HAHN N. & LYLE R., 2019. Spider checklist for the Blouberg, in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, South Africa. *Bothalia* 49(1), a2455. <https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455>.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2009. The Arachnida of the De Hoop Nature Reserve in the Western Cape. *Koedoe* 51: 1–9.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97–122.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WESOLOWSKA W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputaland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1–22.
- JÉZÉQUEL J.-F. 1964. Araignées de la savane de Singrobo (Côte d'Ivoire). III.–Thomisidae. *Bulletin de l'Institut Fondamental d'Afrique Noire (A)* 26(4): 1103–1143.
- LESSERT R. DE. 1919. Araignées du Kilimandjaro et du Mérou (suite). 3. Thomisidae. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 27: 99–234. doi:10.5962/bhl.part.3632
- LESSERT R. DE. 1928. Araignées du Congo recueillies au cours de l'expédition par l'American Museum (1909-1915). Deuxième partie. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 35: 303–352.
- LESSERT R. DE. 1943. Araignées du Congo belge (Troisième partie). *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 50: 305–338.
- RUSSELL-SMITH A. 2020. A checklist of the spiders of Tanzania. *Journal of East African Natural History* 109: 1–41.
- SONG D.X., FENG Z.Q. & SHANG J.W. 1982. On the males of two species of crab spiders (Araneida: Thomisidae). *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* 7: 257–259.
- SIMON E. 1886. Espèces et genres nouveaux de la famille des Thomisidae. *Actes de la Société Linnéenne de Bordeaux* 40: 167–187.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on October 2022. doi: 10.24436/2

First record of the theridiid spider *Rhomphaea affinis* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Araneae: Theridiidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & J. van Zyl²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa. E-mail: dippenaaransie@gmail.com, ²SANSA Team Member Gauteng

ABSTRACT: The Mozambican tailed comb-foot spider, *Rhomphaea affinis* Lessert, 1936, was described from Mozambique and was only known from the type locality. This spider was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Rhomphaea* L. Koch, 1872 is represented by 37 species, and has a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog, 2022). *Rhomphaea* species are still poorly documented in South Africa and only *R. nasicus* (Simon, 1873) was listed in the first Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). Members of *Rhomphaea* differ from other argyrodines by the following putative synapomorphies (Levi & Levi, 1962):

- Abdomen elongate, usually boomerang shaped.
- Posterior tip of abdomen with modified sturdy setae.
- Ocular projection elongate.
- Male palp with embolus tip elongate and strongly ridged basally and palp tibia elongate, but not scoop shaped.
- Egg sac rhomboid shaped (Exline & Levi, 1962).
- Possibly unique prey capture strategy (Whitehouse, 1987; Exline & Levi, 1962).

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936 was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and the first photographs of the species were taken by the second author. Little is still known about them and the aim of this paper is to provide information on their morphology based on live specimens, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. The photographs were taken by the second author and form part of the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936

Rhomphaea affinis Lessert, 1936: 236, f. 31–32 (Df); Agnarsson, 2004: 479.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL: 5–6 mm. Body elongate (Figs 1–2). Carapace as wide as long; bulging towards posterior edge (Fig. 8); fawn with blackish-brown marginal band and two longitudinal lines; blackish-brown parallels from the anterior median eyes reaching the end of the chelicerae. Anterior eyes seen from above are recurved; the medians a little larger than the lateral, very close to the latter. Clypeus slanting, long; chelicerae extend forwards (Fig. 8). Abdomen fawn and decorated with silver spots; elongate, extending past the spinnerets, usually boomerang shape; caudal extremity posterior

Figs 1–2. *Rhomphaea affinis* female in web from Winterton. Photos: Johan van Zyl.

prolonged in small vermiform curved, modified sturdy seta (Figs 4–6). Legs long and slender; femora fawn and decorated with a brown subapical band and dark stripes (Fig. 8). Epigyne a wide atrium with two dark triangular markings on both sides (Fig. 7). Male unknown.

Figs 3–8. *Rhomphaea affinis*: 3. Line drawing of abdomen of female lateral view. 4–6. Close-up of the caudal tip of abdomen showing the curved sturdy seta. 7. Epigyne. 8. Lateral view of the carapace. Credits: 3–4 & 7 after Lessert (1936). 5 & 8. Johan van Zyl. 6. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Mozambique (Bas Mouira, Nhampalamassa) and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Sandveld Nature Reserve Camp (-27.40, 25.41). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Kosi Bay Coastal Forest (-26.57, 32.49); Winterton (-28.81, 29.53).

Map showing distribution in South Africa

BEHAVIOUR

Little is still known about the behaviour of *Rhomphaea* species. These tiny, cryptic spiders are rare and difficult to spot in grasses and bushes and their body shape helps to camouflage them. Research also showed that the spiders with their worm-like abdomens are flexible and are able to change shape. When the abdomen is for example held out long and straight, the spiders look like sticks and blend in with the vegetation they rest on. Exline and Levi (1962) were the first to observe *Rhomphaea* species making their own webs.

In Australia, a *Rhomphaea* sp. was observed by Whitehouse (1987) hanging in the middle of a horizontal web (Fig. 9). The body of the spiders spanned the gap as it rested on the web, but it did not tense the lines or sag them as other spiders do with similar reduced webs. They only came out at night. During the day they rested by hanging about 5 mm below a branch. The *Rhomphaea* sp. by using aggressive mimicry then lures other spiders to then throw a sticky triangular net over the prey (Fig. 10).

In a photograph of *R. affinis* taken in Winterton, a female can be seen hanging in a web with legs II, III, and IV grabbing silk threads (Fig. 11) filling a gap. Unfortunately no prey was near to see whether she will produce a sticky triangle web.

Fig. 9. Web of a *Rhomphaea* sp. located in a bush in Australia. The spider is hanging in the middle of the horizontal thread (After Whitehouse, 1987).

Fig. 10. *Rhomphaea* sp. producing a triangle net just prior to catching prey (After Whitehead, 1987).

Figures 11. *Rhomphaea affinis* female found at night hanging in a sparse web in Winterton. Photo: Johan van Zyl.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

The species is probably under-sampled and might be present in more African countries. There are presently no significant threats to this species but more sampling is needed to collect the male. In South Africa it is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve, Ithala Nature Reserve, Sandveld Nature Reserve, and Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve.

REFERENCES

- AGNARSSON I. 2004. Morphological phylogeny of cobweb spiders and their relatives (Araneae, Araneoidea, Theridiidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 141(4): 447–626.
- BERNHARD W.G. 1979. *Argyrodus attenuatus* (Theridiidae): A web that is not a snare. *Psyche* 86: 407–413.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L., HELBERG L., MATHEBULA S., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN NIEKERK E. & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa. South African National Survey of Arachnida*. SANSa Technical Report version 1 (2010): 1158 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13(1/2): 121–127.
- EXLINE H. & LEVI H. W. 1962. American spiders of the genus *Argyrodus* (Araneae, Theridiidae). *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology* 127(2): 75–202.
- LESSERT R. DE 1936. Araignées de l'Afrique orientale portugaise recueillies par MM. P. Lesne et B.-B. Cott. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 43: 207–306.
- WHITEHOUSE M.E.A. 1987. "Spider eat spider": The predatory behavior of *Rhomphaea* sp. from New Zealand. *Journal of Arachnology* 15: 355–362.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on October 2022. doi: 10.24436/2

Notes on the butterfly crab spider *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886 in South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, B. Blake² & P. Webb³

¹University of Venda, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com, ²SANSA team member KwaZulu-Natal, ³SANSA team member Gauteng

ABSTRACT. *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886 is an African species described from Madagascar. It is rare and known from only a few localities in Madagascar, Gabon, Guinea, and South Africa. The aim of this paper is to add notes on their morphology based on images of living spiders, and to provide information on behaviour and distribution.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). One of the species was identified as *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886. Several photographs were also submitted by the public as part of the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

The genus *Trichopagis* Simon, 1886 is monotypic and data on the type species *T. manicata* described by Simon (1886) from Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2022) is limited to three old papers by Simon (1886, 1895) and Millot (1942). It is a rare spider known from a few localities in Gabon, Guinea, and now South Africa. For the first time, images of live specimens of *T. manicata* were available. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *T. manicata* based on images of live spiders, with notes on their behaviour and distribution.

METHODS

The voucher specimens of *T. manicata* sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Trichopagis manicata Simon, 1886

Trichopagis manicata Simon, 1886: 185 (m); Simon, 1895: 1043; Millot, 1942: 62 (m).

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 5–7 mm, male 4–5 mm. The genus is recognised by the large, dark, club-shaped setae situated in the eye region (Figs 4–5) and on the posterior end of the abdomen (Figs 1 & 6). Carapace semi-circular, as wide as long, and narrowed in eye region (Figs 2 & 13); integument smooth; pale yellow to translucent with a faint greenish tint and thin white marginal band (Fig. 2); eye region covered with a broad red-brown band that extends posteriorly from lateral corners to posterior border (Figs 1 & 3) or sometimes only with two spots (Fig. 15). Eyes in two rows with anterior row narrower than posterior row; the median eyes smaller than the lateral eyes; lateral eyes on small tubercles (Figs 2–3). Carapace provided with two very strong black depressed lanceolate setae at the frontal carapace corners; as well as two similar setae opposite the posterior lateral eyes (Figs 4–5); however, these setae are easily lost. Clypeus with narrow white band; chelicerae brown with dense setae (Fig. 2).

Figs 1–3. *Trichopagis manicata*: 1. Female from Kloof. 2. Female showing eye pattern. 3. Female from Kloof anterior view. Photos: Bruce Blake.

Figures 4–8. *Trichopagis manicata*: 4. Eye pattern showing feathery setae. 5. Male habitus dorsal view. 6. Posterior end of abdomen showing feathery setae. 7. Leg I. 8. Male palp ventral view. 9. Palp retrotibial apophysis (Line drawings 5–9 after Millot, 1942). 10. Female palp (Line drawing after Simon, 1895). 11. Male palp lateral view. 12. Tarsi leg I. 13. Habitus male dorsal view. 14. Habitus male ventral view. Photos: 11–14. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Abdomen longer than wide, with greater width in the posterior third, abdomen shape varies from narrow (Fig. 5) to almost triangular (Figs 1 & 15). Abdomen same pale background as carapace but dorsum decorated with large yellowish brown marking following the contour of the abdomen; colour varies between rich brown to more fawnish brown; two darker spots medially; abdomen ventrally with dark band (Fig. 14); posterior end bears dark club-shaped setae (Fig. 6) that are easily lost. Sternum heart shaped without markings. Legs same colour as carapace; legs I and II in male with distal end of femur and patella dark as well as distal end of tibia and metatarsus (Figs 7, 13–14); tibia and metatarsi I and II with numerous strong paired setae. Palp large with long retrotibial apophysis (Figs 8–9 & 11). Simon (1895) provided a drawing of the thickened tarsi of the palp of a female. In Figs 1–3 & 15–16 the enlarged yellow tarsi could be seen bearing a few strong setae on the border.

Variation: Some colour variation was observed in markings on the carapace and abdomen of the immature specimens from Ndumo; the markings on the carapace consist only of two spots (Fig. 15)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Gabon, Guinea, South Africa, Madagascar.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park; Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.8843, 32.2534); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Hector-spruit (-25.43, 31.68).

Figs 11–12. *Trichopagis manicata* immature: 13. Habitus ,dorsal view. 14. Close-up of eye region and swollen palpi. Photos: Peter Webb.

LIFESTYLE

Trichopagis manicata is a free-living plant dweller sampled from trees and shrubs. It was occasionally found inside flower corollas. Also found on trees and low vegetation. It was sampled in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

This is a rare species. There are no significant threats to this species. Protected in Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2016). Due to its wide range it is listed as Least Concern. No conservation actions are recommended.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae), *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13(1/2): 121–127.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R. & WEBB P. 2016. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 58(1): 1–8.
- HADDAD C.R., HONIBALL A.S., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., SLOTOU R. & VAN RENSBURG B.J. 2010. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in endemic sand forest, Maputaland, South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.
- MILLOT J. 1942. Les araignées de l'Afrique Occidentale Française: Thomisidae. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences de Paris* 65: 1–82.
- SIMON E. 1886. Arachnides recueillis par M. A. Pavie (sous chef du service des postes au Cambodge) dans le royaume de Siam, au Cambodge et en Cochinchine. *Actes de la Société Linnéenne de Bordeaux* 40: 137–166.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, doi: 10.24436/2

Notes on the wolf spider *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878) in South Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & P. Webb²

¹University of Venda (dippenaaransie@gmail.com), ²SANSA team member Gauteng (deceased)

ABSTRACT: The wolf spider *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878) was described as *Lycosa guttata* from Mozambique. It is presently known throughout Central and Southern Africa and more information is provided here on their morphology, distribution in South Africa, and interesting burrow-dwelling behaviour with images of live specimens.

Key words: biodiversity, burrow dweller, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Hippasosa* Roewer, 1960 is represented by 13 species, of which eight are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), a large number of Lycosidae specimens were sampled. One of the species was identified as *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878). The species was described as *Lycosa guttata* from Mozambique in 1878. It was listed for several years as *Ocyale guttata* (Alderweireldt, 1996) and was only recently transferred to *Hippasosa* (Sherwood, 2022). It has been recorded throughout Central and Southern Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

Species of *Hippasosa* are among the larger wolf spiders and colour wise are remarkable wolf spiders. Despite these features, little is known about their biology. The only record on their burrowing behaviour was by Jocqué *et al.* (2017) of *H. ghost* (Jocqué & Jocqué, 2017) in Madagascar.

In this paper the general morphology and burrow-living behaviour of *H. guttata* are discussed and illustrated with photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

The photographs of the species in the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) provided important information on morphology and behaviour. The striking differences between preserved and living specimens stress the importance of documenting live patterns and colours in species descriptions as colours usually fade when specimens are fixed in ethanol. Voucher specimens collected during the SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Hippasosa guttata (Karsch, 1878)

Lycosa guttata Karsch, 1878: 329.

Trochosa guttata Pavesi, 1881: 552.

Crocodylosa guttata Roewer, 1960: 850.

Ocyale guttata Alderweireldt, 1996: 1356, Jocqué *et al.*, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021. (*Ocyale* was declared a nomen dubium (in Pisauridae) by Sherwood (2022).

Hippasosa guttata Sherwood, 2022: 583.

Descriptive characteristics: Female: total length 15–20 mm. Carapace pale brown with paler lateral margins and irregular central markings (Fig. 1). Sternum yellow; clypeus pale yellow; chelicerae pale brown; palp pale brown. Abdomen dorsally greyish with two diverging rows of paler spots, pattern variable (Fig. 2); ventrally pale grey.

Figs 1–3. *Hippasosa guttata* females. Photos: 1. Piet van Dyk. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Figs 4–8. *Hippasosa guttata*: 4. Female's ventral view. 5. Carapace dorsal view. 6. Epigyne. 7. Line drawing male palp. 8. Line drawing epigyne. Photos: 4–6. A. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 7–8. After Alderweireldt (1996).

Legs: Yellow to brown banded (Fig. 3); tibia I ventrally with two pairs of spines and one additional apical pair. Epigyne: Longitudinal pair of inverted T slender and usually as long as transverse part (Figs 6 & 8); lateral margins along median septum well developed, swollen, and shiny. Male: Total length 15–17 mm. Carapace: Darker than female, brown with paler lateral margins and irregular paler central band (Fig. 15). Sternum yellow, somewhat darkened towards edges. Clypeus pale brown; chelicerae brown. Abdomen dorsal surface grey with two rows of white spots, ventral surface pale grey. Legs: Pale brown with darker annulations; tibia I with two pairs of ventral spines and one apical pair. Palp: Pale brown, tarsus somewhat darker (Fig. 7).

HABITAT

The species was sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes. It was also sampled from agri-ecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023).

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-running ground dwellers and were frequently sampled from pitfall traps. They are very well camouflaged and blend in with their surroundings (Fig. 15) (Webb, 2014). Little is known about their general behaviour.

The first observations on their burrow-dwelling behaviour were made while sampling at Ezemvelo Nature Reserve in Gauteng. The second author found a spider burrow, about 9 mm across, lined with silk (Fig. 11) one late evening. As there was no spider visible, he decided to examine the burrow in the morning. However, the next morning no traces of the burrow could be found. After scanning the area he did eventually find the burrow (Fig. 10). It was closed over with a soft silk flap, well camouflaged with sand particles (Fig. 9). The flap was a floppy extension of the tunnel itself and when open it forms a rim around the burrow entrance on the ground (Fig. 12). To close the entrance, the spider lifts the flap and pulls it towards the centre, forming a sand-covered soft trapdoor. The burrow entrance remained closed during the day, but in the evening, it was open, and the spider was observed sitting in the entrance (Fig. 12) and seen leaving the burrow (Fig. 13).

Figs 9–14. Burrow of *Hippasosa guttata* as observed at the Ezemvelo Nature Reserve. Photos: Peter Webb.

Fig. 15. *Hippasosa guttata* blending in with surroundings. Photo: Piet Grobler.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Hippasosa guttata is known from eight African countries: Botswana, Mozambique, Namibia, Rwanda, Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe, and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022). In South Africa, it is known from four provinces: KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga, Gauteng, and Limpopo (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010).

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide global distribution. In South Africa it is sampled from seven protected areas with two published surveys: Kruger National Park (Robertson *et al.*, 2011) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (Crocodile Farm) (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Scottburgh (-30.28, 30.75); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6181, 32.2294); Umseleni (-28.33, 31.08). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Klein Letaba (-23.13, 30.43); Wood-bush Forest Reserve (-23.78, 30.07); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Vhembe Biosphere Gonden (Communal land)(-24.905, 29.994); Vyeboom (-24.77, 28.47). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-24.99, 31.59); Kruger National Park: Skukuza-Malelane (-25.109, 31.624).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Piet van Dyk and Piet Grobler for sharing their photographs.

REFERENCES

- ALDERWEIRELDT M. 1996. A taxonomic revision of the genus *Ocyale* Audouin, 1826 in Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae). *Journal of Natural History* 30: 1349–1365.
- ALDERWEIRELDT M. & JOCQUÉ R. 2005. A taxonomic review of the Afrotropical representatives of the genus *Hippasa* (Araneae, Lycosidae). *Journal of Afrotropical Zoology* 2: 45–68.
- BÖSENBERG W. & LENZ H. 1895. Ostafrikanische Spinnen gesammelt von Herrn Dr. F. Stuhlmann in den Jahren 1888 und 1889. *Jahrbuch der Hamburgischen Wissenschaftlichen Anstalten* 12(2): 27–51.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2021. *The Lycosidae of South Africa*. Version 1: part 2 (L-Z). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 82 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6324723
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., HELBERG L., MATHEBULA S., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN NIEKERK E. & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida. SANSa Technical Report version 1 (2010): 1158 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. AND LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., SCHOEMAN C., HAHN N. & LYLE R. 2019. Spider checklist for the Blouberg in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, South Africa. *Bothalia* 49(1), a2455. <https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455>.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WESOLOWSKA W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputoland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1–22.
- JOCQUÉ M., WELLENS S., ANDRIANARIVOSOA J.D., RAKOTONDRAPARANY F., THE SEING S. & JOCQUÉ, R. 2017. A new species of *Ocyale* (Araneae, Lycosidae) from Madagascar, with first observations on the biology of a representative in the genus. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 355: 1–13.
- KARSCH F. 1878. Übersicht der von Peters in Mossambique gesammelten Arachniden. *Monatsberichte der Königlich Preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin* 1878: 314–338.
- PAVESI P. 1881. Studi sugli Aracnidi africani. II. Aracnidi d'Inhambane raccolti da Carlo Fornasini e considerazioni sull'aracnofauna del Mozambico. *Annali del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale di Genova* 16: 536–560.
- ROBERTSON M.P., HARRIS K.R., COETZEE J., FOXCROF L., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN RENSBURG B.J. 2011. Assessing local scale impacts of *Opuntia stricta* (Cactaceae) invasion on beetle and spider diversity in the Kruger National Park, South Africa. *African Zoology* 46: 205–223.
- ROEWER C.F. 1960. Araneae Lycosaeformia II (Lycosidae) (Fortsetzung und Schluss). *Exploration du Parc National de l'Upemba, Mission G. F. de Witte* 55: 519–1040.
- SHERWOOD D. 2022. On the taxonomic and nomenclatural status of *Ocyale* Audouin, 1826 (Araneae: Pisauridae) and *Hippasosa* Roewer, 1960 (Araneae: Lycosidae), with notes on some other taxa. *Arachnology* 19(2): 582–584.
- STRAND E. 1908. Nordafrikanische, hauptsächlich von Carlo Freiherr von Erlanger gesammelte Lycosiden. *Archiv für Naturgeschichte* 73(I, 3, 1907): 291–376.
- WEBB P. 2014. Unusual sighting of a burrow-living wolf spider. *SANSa Newsletter* 20: 6.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2022. World Spider Catalog. Version 23.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 15 October 2022. doi: 10.24436/2

South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng province, South Africa

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Johan van Zyl²

¹University of Venda, South Africa (dippenaaransie@gmail.com); ²SANSA team member Gauteng.

Abstract: The first checklist of the spider species of Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve in Gauteng, South Africa, is presented. Spiders were collected over a period of 10 years, and 37 families, represented by 113 genera and 142 species, are listed. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (24 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (15 spp.), Gnaphosidae (14 spp.), and Araneidae (13 spp.), while 18 families are singletons. Information on the endemism and conservation status of each species is provided as well as a photo gallery of some species. Approximately 6% of the total South African spider fauna are protected in the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve.

Key words: endemism, conservation status, photo gallery

INTRODUCTION

Gauteng is one of the nine provinces of South Africa and covers an area of approximately 17 800 km², accounting for only 1.5% of the South African land area. It was previously known as part of the Transvaal province until South Africa's first democratic elections on 27 April 1994. The province falls within both the Savanna and highly threatened Grassland biomes and approximately 83% of the province falls within Highveld Grassland vegetation types, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa (Pfab, 2001).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) that was initiated in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), extensive sampling took place in the Gauteng province. Presently, 561 species are known from this small province but only a few papers have yet been published on spider surveys of the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014). These include surveys at the Roodeplaat Research Station (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976), Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991), and Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022).

The aim of this study is to provide a first checklist of the spider fauna of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (SRNR), near Heidelberg in Gauteng. The annotated checklist is accompanied by levels of endemism and conservation status data on each species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The SRNR (-25.8, 28.77) is located about an hour's drive from Oliver Tambo International Airport and near the town of Heidelberg, in Gauteng. The reserve (134 km²) is situated in the Suikerbosrand Range in the rocky Highveld Grassland Biome (Figs 1–3). The altitude varies between 1 545 and 1 917 m above sea level.

The Suikerbosrand ridge was originally named after a sweet reed found growing here in 1836. Later the ridge and consequently the reserve's name became associated with the characteristic Transvaal sugarbush (*Protea caffra*), a dominant vegetation type within the reserve. The reserve falls within the summer rainfall area, with hot summers and cold winters with frost. Hail is common during summer thunderstorms. Maximum temperatures in midwinter average 19 °C and the minimum average is 5 °C. Midsummer maximum temperatures average 28 °C and the minimum average is 17 °C.

Figs 1–3. Some of the the habitat types in the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve. Photos: Johan van Zyl.

Fig. 3. Study area Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng.

Fig. 4. Entrance to the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve.

Study period and methods: Spiders were collected over a period of several years from 2009 to 2020 using different collecting methods to sample both the ground and field layers. The surveys were undertaken by:

- Members of the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council.
- Students of the North-West University during their annual survey activities in 2009–2010.
- Members of the Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDARD) then known as Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDACE) as part of their Gauteng Biodiversity GAP Analysis Project (Pfab, 2001).
- The second author lives next to the reserve and he regularly photographed spiders from the reserve.

Identification, photography and voucher specimens: Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the NCA at the Agricultural Research Council-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Tables 1 & 3). The photographs were donated to the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species were determined (Table 3) based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 = when SRNR is the type locality.
- 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality.
- 4 = SAE, endemic to South Africa but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 = SAE, South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers).
- 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic).
- 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 142 species from 37 families and 113 genera are presently known from SRNR. Three species (Sparassidae and Zodariidae) could not be identified to species level as they were still immature.

Family diversity: Of the 37 spider families collected from SRNR (Tables 1 & 3), the Salticidae with 24 species is the most diverse family, followed by Thomisidae (15 spp.), Gnaphosidae (14 spp.), and Araneidae (13 spp.) (Table 1). Eighteen species are known from only a single species.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve listing the total number of families, genera (G), and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	G	SPP.	FAMILIES	G	SPP.
Agelenidae	2	2	Philodromidae	4	6
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	2
Araneidae	11	13	Phyxelididae	2	2
Bemmeridae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Prodidomidae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Salticidae	17	24
Corinnidae	2	2	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	2	Sparassidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	10	14	Tetragnathidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Idiopidae	1	1	Theridiidae	7	7
Linyphiidae	2	2	Thomisidae	9	15
Liocranidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Lycosidae	9	14	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Oecobiidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Oxyopidae	3	3	Zodariidae	5	6
Palpimanidae	1	1	37 FAMILIES	113	142

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species recorded from the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve

Conservation status	No. spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	0	DD	0
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	3	NE	2.1
Least concern	138	LC	97.9
Vulnerable	0	VU	0
Near threatened	0	NT	0
Endemism			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	17	LC	12.1
1 – African endemics (AE)	59	LC	41.8
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	30	LC	21.3
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	29	LC	20.6
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	4	LC	2.8
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	0	VU,NT	0
6 – Type locality	0	0	0

Conservation status: The majority (97.9%) of species have a wide distribution and without known threats and are listed as Least Concern. The three species not evaluated were still immature. None of the species recorded are of special concern.

Endemism: Seventeen species (12.1%) sampled at SRNR have a wider distribution than Africa (C), while 41.8% are known from Africa (AE) and 21.3% are known from Southern Africa and only 2.8% are South African endemics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank all the people who have sampled spiders in the reserve and made them available as voucher specimens in the NCA.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1979. Spider communities in strawberry beds: Seasonal changes in numbers and species composition. *Phytophylactica* 11: 1–4.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LYLE R. 2014. Several SANSA projects underway – three new projects in Gauteng. *SANSA Newsletter* 20: 10.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13(1/2): 121–127.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1989. Species composition and relative seasonal abundance of spiders from the field and tree layers of the Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve. *Koedoe* 32: 51–60.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2022. Gauteng Urban Surveys 1. Checklist of the spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 41: 26–34.

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: Patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48:110–118.

LYLE R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2013. Grassland project: Spider surveys in Gauteng grassland. *Plant Protection News* 97: 1–2.

PFAB M. 2001. The Gauteng Biodiversity GAP Analysis Project. An unpublished report. Gauteng Nature Conservation, DACEL.

VAN DEN BERG A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1991. Ground-living spiders from an area where the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* occurs in South Africa. *Phytophylactica* 23: 247–253.

Figs 5–20. 5–12: Araneidae: 5. *Caerostris sexcupidata*. 6. *Eriovixia excelsa*. 7. *Neoscona subfusca*. 8. *Cyphalonotus larvatus*. 9. *Neoscona moreli*. 10. *Trichonephila fenestrata*. 11. *Pararaneus cyrtoscapus*. 12. *Neoscona hirta*. 13. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Cheiracanthiidae). 14. *Clubiona pongolensis* (Clubionidae). 15. *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Cyrtaucheniidae). 16. *Menneus camelus* (Deinopidae). 17. *Setaphis subtilis* (Gnaphosidae). 18. *Microlinyphia sterilis* (Linyphiidae). 19. *Proevippa albiventris* (Lycosidae). 20. *Oecobius navus* (Oecobiidae). Photos: Johan van Zyl.

21

22

23

24

25

26

27

28

29

30

31

32

33

34

35

Figures 21–35. 21. *Hamataliwa kulczynskii* (Oxyopidae). 22. *Philodromus guineensis* (Philodromidae). 23. *Thanatus atlanticus* (Philodromidae). 24. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pisauridae). 25. *Euprostenops australis* (Pisauridae). 26. *Baryphas ahenus* (Salticidae). 27. *Heliophanus transvaalicus* (Salticidae). 28. *Thyene natalii* (Salticidae). 29. *Heliophanus patellaris* (Salticidae). 30. *Tidarren cuneolatum* (Theridiidae). 31. *Runcinia aethiops* (Thomisidae). 32. *Simorcus cotti* (Thomisidae). 33. *Synema imitatrix* (Thomisidae). 34. *Thomisus citrinellus* (Thomisidae). 35. *Platyoides walteri* (Trochanteriidae). Photos: Johan van Zyl.

TABLE 3. Checklist of the spiders species recorded from the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve in Gauteng with information on their endemicity (ENDV), conservation status (CON), country endemicity (CEND), and provincial endemics (PROVE). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	ENDV	CON	CEND
1. Agelenidae	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
2. Amaurobiidae	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
3. Araneidae	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	4. Bemmeridae	<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC
5. Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
6. Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona pongolensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
7. Corinnidae	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
8. Cyrtaucheniidae	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa nigriceps</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE
9. Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
10. Eresidae	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dresserus kannemeyeri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	LC	SAE
11. Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala lapidaria</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Marinarozelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	0	LC	C
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	1	LC	AE
	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
	<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
12. Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
13. Idiopidae	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
14. Linyphiidae	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
15. Liocranidae	<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE

TABLE 3 continue

16. Lycosidae	<i>Allocosa nebulosa</i> (Roewer, 1960)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hippasa funerea</i> Lessert, 1925	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1960)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
	17. Oecobiidae	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC
18. Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
19. Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
20. Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus atlanticus</i> Berland, 1936	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
21. Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
22. Phyxelididae	<i>Pongolania chrysonaria</i> Griswold, 1990	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole lyra</i> Griswold, 1990	3	LC	SAE
23. Pisauridae	<i>Cispus variegatus</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
24. Prodidomidae	<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
25. Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dendryphantes hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
	<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus aberdarensis</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus patellaris</i> Simon, 1901	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE

Table 3 continue

	<i>Magrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
	<i>Myrmarachne uvira</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesołowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesołowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesołowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
26. Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
27. Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer, 1837	0	LC	C
28.. Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Anyphops lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
29. Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes</i> sp. imm.			NE
30. Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
31. Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
30. Theridiidae	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
31. Thomisidae	<i>Ansia tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
	<i>Smodicinus coroniger</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
32. Trachelidae	<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
33. Trochanteriidae	<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE
34. Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C

Table 3 continue

35. Zodariidae	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores rectus</i> Jocqué, 1990	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Microdiores</i> sp. *			NE
	<i>Ranops</i> sp. *			NE
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE